

THE ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL MARKETING MANAGEMENT: THE CASE OF TÜRKIYE

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Abstract: One of the economically important issues today is marketing and ensuring the effective management of the marketing process. Because if the goods produced are sold, they will have an economic meaning. For this reason, it is extremely important to effectively market the produced goods. In this process, successfully planning, implementing and managing marketing activities for goods and services produced in a country provides significant advantages to that country. With successful marketing management, first of all, the recognition of goods and services produced in a country increases in both national and international markets. In this way, increases in production volume may occur due to increases in demand. This allows economic vitality to increase and economic growth to occur. In addition, the successful implementation of management strategies for marketing goods produced in the country in international markets contributes to the increase in export volume. Because successful marketing of products in international markets gives that country competitive power and superiority in international markets. It is possible to say that marketing management consists of four stages called analysis, planning, implementation, guidance and control, and each of these stages has a different importance. With this prepared study, the economic importance of international marketing management in Türkiye will be revealed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Businesses engage in a series of activities that are compatible with each other in order to deliver the goods and/or services they produce to final consumers. Examinations carried out to determine how and in what form these activities will occur, created plans, putting these plans into practice and organizing and managing constitutes marketing management. Marketing is the activity of providing the needed goods or services at the right price, in the right place, at the right time, at a profit. According to another definition, marketing is a system of interrelated business activities that organize planning, pricing, distribution and sales activities to provide existing and potential consumers with the goods and services needed to meet their needs. Marketing is a set of processes that include all activities between producers, consumers, goods and services. The consumer is at the center of this process. The most basic goal is to provide customer satisfaction. Because consumers who are satisfied and whose demands are met become loyal customers over time, and thus the future income sources of the business are guaranteed. In this sense, it is possible to talk about two main purposes of marketing. These are to determine consumer demands and needs and to offer the products produced in line with these demands to consumer preference (Bilginer, 2023: 226).

Over time, changes have occurred in consumption habits due to the increase in consumers' education and communication levels. In addition, the acceleration of globalization due to developments in technology has caused some changes in the understanding of marketing. This new marketing approach is described as “classical marketing”, and the previous marketing approach is described as “traditional marketing”. The traditional marketing approach is a marketing approach based on the superiority of the concepts of “production/product” and “sales” adopted in the 1920s. However, especially after the World Crisis that started in the 1930s and the Second World War, the need for a stronger market along with the importance of business strategies led to the emergence of marketing strategies. In addition, developments in the following years have made it necessary to develop new approaches that are newer and more effective than the previous ones. It is seen that studies in the field of marketing have been under the influence of marketing mix and marketing management since the 1960s. In this period, the main purpose of the traditional marketing

approach focusing on consumer goods and consumer markets was to reach the optimum marketing mix. The main purpose of traditional marketing is to create the most appropriate product, price, distribution and promotion mix. The most important element of the change in the marketing process is that while traditional marketing has a business-oriented structure, the new marketing approach has a customer-oriented structure. However, there are differences between the two different approaches in terms of the way they do business. In traditional marketing, the aim is to maximize profits by selling to more people, and customer behaviors, characteristics and purchasing history are not considered. In traditional marketing approaches until the new marketing approach, the customer was always ignored and remained in the background in production/product and sales issues. Over time, marketing activities have evolved depending on globalization, the development of technology and the increase in both the education and communication levels of consumers. In this process, the definition of marketing, the marketing mix, its role and the organizational structure of the business have also changed. In the process of change, relationship marketing has developed, the customer has been placed at the focal point of the business, and the concepts of value creation and value transfer have developed (Alabay, 2010: 214-215).

2. DEFINITION, IMPORTANCE AND FUNCTIONS OF MARKETING

Under this heading, information on the concept of marketing will be given, followed by information on the importance of marketing and the functions of marketing.

2.1. Marketing and Its Importance

Marketing is the sum of the activities involved in the transfer of products and services from the producer or seller to the consumer or buyer, including advertising, transportation, storage and sales. According to a more recent definition, marketing is the planning and implementation process of developing, pricing, promoting and distributing ideas, goods and services in order to realize exchanges that will achieve personal and organizational goals. With technological developments, information technologies have begun to be used in many areas of marketing. Especially with the development of the internet, digital marketing, which consists of many subheadings such as e-marketing, online marketing and social media marketing, is becoming more widespread and developing (Girgin, 2019: 3-4).

Marketing is a management-oriented concept that states that success depends, first of all, on understanding changing customer demands accurately and before competitors, and also on developing better products than competitors. Marketing is about accurately understanding customers' wants. In this context, businesses are looking for new ways and techniques to satisfy customers' demands and needs through marketing. One of these is strategic marketing. Strategic marketing deals with how businesses should act in the process of interaction with competitors, customers and consumers in the market in the context of the production, delivery and communication of products that offer value to customers. Strategic marketing aims to design a plan to achieve long-term goals such as increasing efficiency and profitability and meeting customer needs, as well as improving the overall performance of the business. Strategic marketing decisions in small businesses have a significant impact on other functional areas of the business and are of great importance in terms of business performance, financial performance and long-term survival of the business. While marketing in general terms refers to all the steps taken by the organization in establishing beneficial relationships with customers, strategic marketing refers to the plans made by the company to attract customers in order to dominate the market. While the important tools and techniques of marketing consist of the marketing mix known as the 4Ps (product, price, distribution, promotion), strategic marketing uses the 3Cs (competitors, customers, organization) as tools. While marketing promotes the brand and the offers offered, strategic marketing helps the business grow and succeed by gaining superiority over its competitors (Şaylan et al. 2023: 644).

Today, in order to compete in domestic and international markets, a business has to determine the production method, determine the capacity utilization rate, determine the goals and policies in pricing, decide on distribution channels, and finally learn the socio-economic structure and cultural characteristics of the targeted market. Efforts to increase the ability of produced goods to meet consumer needs lead businesses to be more sensitive about quality. At this point, businesses obtain important data on what kind of goods and

services are needed in the market, how these goods will be marketed domestically and internationally, and finally how they will be delivered to the consumer by conducting marketing research. As a result, businesses produce and conduct various marketing activities in order to provide consumer satisfaction with a reasonable profit rate and to make this sustainable. In this process, businesses' achievement of their financial goals generally depends on their marketing ability. Because reaching a sufficient demand level for goods and services that will enable the company to make a reasonable profit is possible thanks to marketing. In other words, trade is realized to a significant extent thanks to marketing activities. Trade is realized through the sale of goods and services, and sales generally occur as a result of marketing. In this process, it is of great importance to produce goods and services in line with customer demands at a low cost, without compromising on quality, by observing cost leadership. Applying appropriate pricing methods according to the purpose and ensuring the supply and logistics of raw materials, semi-finished products and final products at the appropriate place and time are issues that require being effective in production management and marketing. It is a desired situation to deliver the right goods, in the right quantity, to the right address with successful physical distribution management (Selvi and Işık, 2015: 30-31)

2.2. Marketing Functions

Marketing functions are system and management functions applied on the path the product takes from the producer to the consumer. Marketing system functions consist of three basic elements. These are change, physical distribution and facilitating functions (Özüdoğru, 2010).

However, it is seen that these functions change over time. The pace of change and renewal process of technology progresses much faster every day. As a result of the increase in the speed of movement of technology and the fact that every innovation brings a change, great differences have occurred in the functioning of social life and institutional life. While people's behaviors and habits shift towards a different axis depending on the new order enabled by technology, commercial institutions' relationships and communication with their customers have also changed. This change has brought different strategies and marketing methods with it. While marketing communication elements, in which communication with the customer has gained importance as opposed to traditional marketing methods, have come to the fore, the concept of integrated marketing communication, which requires the harmonious use of all elements of marketing communication, has emerged over time with technology. It is an undeniable fact that collecting, measuring and evaluating data leads to clearer results for researchers and researchers thanks to the opportunities provided by technology. This new marketing world, enabled by technology, the Internet and new communication technologies, has enabled institutions to use a new method called digital marketing in reaching their target audiences (Bulunmaz, 2016: 348)

2.3. Marketing Management Processes

We have previously stated that marketing is, in general, the sum of the creation, pricing, distribution and sales efforts of products (goods, services, ideas, thoughts) in order to meet the needs and desires of individuals and organizations and to realize change. The planning, organization, execution and control of these actions is called marketing management (Taşkın and Kosat, 2022: 2).

The marketing management process consists of four stages: analysis of market opportunities, selection of target markets, development and creation of the marketing mix and management of marketing efforts (Kotler and Armstrong, 2005). The first stage of the marketing management process is the analysis of market opportunities. Due to the variable structure of the markets (new opportunities and new risks), every business needs to research and find new market opportunities. For this reason, businesses should follow the opportunities suitable for their own goals and resources and analyze the environment well. Managers should evaluate the economic, demographic, legal and political factors that affect the environment, etc. should be informed about the factors and should know the factors such as consumers, competitors and intermediary institutions well in the marketing process. The second stage of the marketing management process is the selection of target markets. Businesses cannot meet the needs of all consumers in a certain market at the same level. Since there are many types of consumers with different needs, the business selects certain segments of the market and offers products and services suitable for these segments. Therefore, the business

should examine the entire market well and select the market segments where it can have a competitive advantage as target markets. This process consists of three stages. These are market segmentation, market targeting and market positioning. The third stage of the marketing management process is the development of the marketing mix. The marketing mix is the combination of controllable marketing variables (product, price, promotion and place) that the business creates in order to be successful in the target market. In order to create a solid marketing strategy, businesses should focus their efforts and energies on the market segments that they can serve best in terms of competition and try to create the most suitable mix. The last stage of the marketing management process is the management of marketing activities. Managers responsible for marketing activities should develop competitive strategies by considering their own situation and resources and the situation and resources of their competitors and ensure that these strategies adapt to changing conditions. Marketing strategies created for this purpose should be compatible with both consumer needs and competitor strategies (Mucuk, 2010). In line with all this information, it is possible to say that the main purpose of marketing management is to provide competitive power to the business through effective marketing programs. Therefore, it is of great importance that basic marketing management functions such as planning, implementation and control are used effectively and efficiently by businesses in order to gain competitive power in the markets.

2.4. Importance of International Marketing Management in Terms of Turkish Economy

When determining international marketing strategies, it is accepted that consumers in foreign markets have different expectations, desires and needs than domestic customers. Accordingly, marketing policies differ. In this process, first of all, it should be determined which goods will be in demand in which markets and then the necessary pricing, distribution and promotion studies should be carried out. In order for each country to increase its export revenues, it needs to produce goods that it has competitive power in international markets. This situation naturally applies to Turkey as well. Turkey's production and marketing of goods that it has high competitive power for international markets will allow the country to increase its success in international markets (Çengel, 2008: 67-68). The goods in which Turkey has a relatively high competitive power in international markets are carpets and floor coverings, ready-made articles and sets made of textile materials, profiles made of iron or steel, knitted garments for men and women, radiators (non-electric) made of lime, cement and natural stones and asphalt, iron, steel and ceramics, wires, ropes, semi-finished products and cables made of aluminum, copper or iron-steel, television receivers and accessories. On the other hand, the goods in which Turkey has a relatively low competitive power in international markets are; food processing machines, rubber inner and outer tires, woven fabrics made of textile materials, tanks, cisterns made of iron, steel or aluminum, etc. containers, rubber and articles made of rubber, paper, pulp, cardboard and articles made of cellulosic fibers, firearms and war materials, glass, tractors, ships and floating vehicles, articles made of plastic, sheets and plates made of plastics (Sarıçoban et al. 2015: 59-62). These products are the products that are traded in international markets. For Turkey, especially turning to markets that have not yet reached saturation brings success in marketing processes and enables increases in export volume. In this context, it is of great importance for Turkey to intensify its marketing activities towards highly competitive goods (Çengel, 2008: 68)

3. CONCLUSION

One of the important elements of the development process in terms of national economies is the increase in production and the sales of these products. Because this way, incomes can be obtained and the incomes obtained are transferred to the production process again, contributing to the production of new products and the realization of economic growth. However, production alone is not enough for economic development to occur. In addition, there is a need to promote the products that have been produced and to make consumers aware of these products. Only in this way can the production that is carried out gain economic value. Marketing activities constitute one of the most important elements of this process. Thanks to an effective marketing activity, consumers can be informed about the products and create a demand for those products in line with their needs. Otherwise, it is not expected for a consumer who is not aware of the existence of a product that they need to create any demand for goods and services. For this reason, marketing

activities are extremely important for the realization of economic growth. In addition, transferring marketing activities to international markets will also contribute to the increase in the export volume of the country. Because the promotion of goods and services produced in a country in international markets causes an increase in the demand for those goods and services. In addition, thanks to an effective marketing process, national goods can gain competitive power in international markets. These developments lead to an increase in the national production volume and naturally to the revival of the economy. In this context, due to the contributions it provides to the economy, attention should be paid to the development of marketing activities. Turkey has a competitive advantage in some goods in international markets. It is possible to say that effective marketing activities carried out for international markets have an effect on this advantage. Because thanks to marketing activities, Turkish goods are recognized in international markets and demands for these goods are created. The goods that Turkey has competitive power in international markets are, in the most general sense, carpets, clothing items, iron or steel profiles and radiators, cement derivatives, aluminum, copper, iron or steel wires and semi-finished cables, television receivers and accessories. On the other hand, Turkey's competitive power in international markets is low in food processing machines, rubber inner and outer tires, iron and steel or aluminum warehouses, rubber and rubber products, paper derivatives, firearms and materials, glass products, tractors, ships and floating vehicles and plastic products. In line with this information, Turkey should adopt an effective and strategic marketing management and implement it resolutely in order to further increase its competitive power in international markets for the goods it has competitive power in and to gain competitive power in the goods it does not have competitive power. In this way, the recognition of national goods in international markets will increase and demand for these goods will increase, thus increasing export volume and export revenues, which will directly contribute to economic growth. Therefore, adopting an effective strategic marketing management and implementing it meticulously is extremely important in terms of ensuring economic development.

References

- [1]. Alabay, N. (2010). Geleneksel Pazarlamadan Yeni Pazarlama Yaklaşımlarına Geçiş Süreci, Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi, 15(2), 213-235.
- [2]. Bilginer, E. (2023). Operasyonları Yönetmek, Eczacılıkta İşletme ve Yönetim, (Eds. G. Özçelikay, M. Çalığışu ve M. B. Uzun), Ankara: Akademisyen Kitabevi
- [3]. Bulunmaz, B. (2016). Gelişen Teknolojiyle Birlikte Değişen Pazarlama Yöntemleri ve Dijital Pazarlama. TRT Akademi, 1(2), 348-365.
- [4]. Çengel, Ö. (2008). Küreselleşme Sürecinin Uluslararası Pazarlama Stratejilerine Etkileri ve Çin Örneği, Öneri Dergisi, 8(29), 65-69.
- [5]. Girgin, M. (2019). Pazarlama ve Veri Analitiği; Pazarlamanın Artan Önemi. Uluslararası Bankacılık Ekonomi ve Yönetim Araştırmaları Dergisi, 2(2), 1-29.
- [6]. Kotler, P. ve Armstrong, G. (2005). Principles of Marketing, 11th ed. Prentice-Hall International, Upper Saddle River, N.J.
- [7]. Mucuk, İ. (2010). Pazarlama İlkeleri ve Yönetimi için Örnek Olaylar, Türkmen Kitabevi, İstanbul.
- [8]. Özüdoğru, H. (2010). Kooperatiflerde Pazarlama. Ziraat Mühendisliği Dergisi, (354), 58-64.
- [9]. Sarıçoban, K., Kösekahyaoğlu, L., & Erkan, B. (2017). Türkiye'nin İmalat Sanayi Ürün Gruplarındaki İhracat Rekabet Gücünün Belirlenmesi: 1996- 2015 Dönemi Analizi. Journal of Life Economics, 4(3), 49-72.
- [10]. Selvi, M. S., & Işık, G. (2016). İşletmelerin Pazarlama Faaliyetlerine İlişkin Nitel Bir Araştırma. International Anatolia Academic Online Journal Social Sciences Journal, 3(1), 29-39.

- [11]. Şaylan, O., Esmer, Y., & Çelik, P. (2023). Kobi`Lerde Stratejik Pazarlama Yönetimi: Lüleburgaz Örneği. *Journal of Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Economics and Administrative Sciences Faculty*, 10(1), 639-657.
- [12]. Taşkın, E., & Kosat, A. (2022). Sürdürülebilir Kalkınmanın Rekabet Gücü ve Şehir Markalaşmasına Etkisi: TR 33 Bölgesi Üzerine Nitel Bir Araştırma. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, (72), 1-24.